

Spikelet fertility of IR64446-7-3-2-2, IR65598-112-2, and their testcross F₁s with indica and japonica testers. IRRI.

Line/F ₁	Spikelet fertility (%)	Difference in spikelet fertility (%) from ^a	
		Indica × japonica F ₁	Tester parent mean spikelet
IR64446-7-3-2-2	57.8 ± 4.5	+21.9**	-26.6**
(IR64446-7-3-2-2/IR36) F ₁	89.1 ± 4.3	+53.2**	4.7
(IR64446-7-3-2-2/Taichung 65) F ₁	84.3 ± 6.6	+48.4**	-0.1
IR65598-112-2	79.6 ± 5.6	+43.7**	-4.8
(IR65598-112-2/IR36) F ₁	87.5 ± 5.6	+51.6**	3.1
(IR65598-112-2/Taichung 65) F ₁	83.7 ± 7.7	+47.8**	-0.7
IR36	81.2 ± 5.3	-	-
Taichung 65	87.6 ± 6.5	-	-
(IR36/Taichung 65) F ₁	35.9 ± 6.5	-	-

** = significant at the 0.01% level.

parental lines possesses the wide compatibility (WC) gene(s).

We screened 10 improved tropical japonica lines (IR64446-7-1-2-3, IR64446-7-3-2-2, IR64446-7-8-2-2, IR64446-7-10-2-2, IR64454-6-8-5-3, IR64454-36-1-5-3, IR64454-81-1-3-2, IR65597-25-1, IR65597-134-2, and IR65598-112-2) for WC trait by crossing these, on a single plant basis, with indica (IR36) and japonica (Taichung 65) testers. Selfed seed of the parental lines and testers was also collected.

Parental lines, testers (IR36 and Taichung 65), and their F₁s were grown at IRRI during 1993 WS. Each F₁ was grown in a plot of two rows (12 plants each) and each parental line in a single-row plot. Two rows of IR36/Taichung 65 F₁ were also grown. Two healthy panicles from each plant of every F₁ or parental line were sampled to determine spikelet fertility.

All 10 tropical japonica lines exhibited normal fertility in crosses with japonica (Taichung 65) tester. Testcross F₁s involving 8 of the 10 tropical japonica

lines with an indica tester showed partial fertility (42.6-68.3% spikelet fertility). Testcross F₁s involving IR64446-7-3-2-2 (MD2/Pakistan) and IR65598-112-2 (Shen Nung 89-366 Gendjah Wangkal), however, showed spikelet fertility either similar to or higher than that of the parental and tester lines (see table), although IR64446-7-3-2-2 showed less than normal fertility (57.8%).

Lines IR64446-7-3-2-2 and IR65598-112-2 are therefore considered to possess the WC trait. Both lines are semidwarf and possess the characteristics of IRRI's new plant type: fewer tillers and larger panicles than current modern high-yielding varieties.

IR65598-112-2 was also found to be a maintainer for the wild abortive cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line; testcross F₁ (IR62829 A/IR65598-112-2) showed all plants to have complete pollen sterility.

We are converting this line into a CMS line and are also incorporating the thermosensitive genic male sterility (TGMS) gene into the two lines. The CMS and TGMS lines may be useful for developing indica/tropical japonica rice hybrids. ■

Natural outcrossing potential in cytoplasmic male sterile lines of rice

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We studied the outcrossing potential of cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines of wild abortive (WA) origin along with

their promising restorers. A crossing block was raised with four CMS lines (V20 A, ZS97 A, IR58025 A, and IR62829 A) and five restorers (IR24, IR54742-22-19-3, IR29723-143-3-2-1, IR9761-19-1, and ARC11353) in a randomized complete block design with two replications during 1993 kharif (Jun-Sep). Seed setting percentage was calculated for 20 cross combinations. An A to R row ratio of 4:2 was adopted; 10 plants for both A and R lines were maintained in each row at a

spacing of 20 × 10 cm. Three rows of Purple Puttu served as pollen barriers around the crossing block and between each cross combination. Rice was planted across the wind direction and allowed to pollinate naturally. Seeds were collected for individual A × R combinations at maturity. We used the mean of 40 plants in each A line replication for analysis.

Seed setting percentage was significantly different among cross combinations using analysis of variance. Mean outcrossing was high in V20 A (16.4%) and IR58025 A (16.4%) when interplanted with different restorers (see table), meaning that these lines can be used in hybrid rice breeding programs.

Individual combinations IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R (20.5%), IR58025 A/IR24 R (18.9%), V20 A/IR24 R (18.9%) V20 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R (18.8%), and ZS97 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R (18.2%) showed the highest outcrossing. These crosses can produce more hybrid seed in a unit area than the others. ■

Natural outcrossing (%) on four A lines planted along with five R lines. Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India. 1993 kharif.

Restorer (Pollen source)	Outcrossing rate (%) in CMS lines			
	V20 A	ZS97 A	IR58025 A	IR62829 A
IR24	18.9	12.2	18.9	2.2
IR54742-22-19-3	13.1	16.1	16.6	1.2
IR29723-143-3-2-1	18.8	18.2	20.5	11.5
IR9761-19-1	15.5	10.2	9.5	5.5
ARC11353	15.6	9.3	16.4	12.0
Mean	16.4	13.2	16.4	6.5
CD (0.05)	0.4			